

Investigation of Starch Degrading Enzyme Activity of Isolated Soil Bacteria on Different Starch Substrates

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Abstract

Amylases, which are essential in biological and industrial applications, are enzymes that break down complex starch into simpler sugars like glucose and maltose through hydrolysis. Due to their stability, ease of production, and ability to operate under a wide range of environmental conditions, microbial amylases are preferred in industrial applications. This study aimed to identify commonly available and cost-effective substrates that support the optimal growth of starch-degrading soil bacteria and promote the production of amylase. Pure soil bacterial isolates were obtained by sequential streaking on nutrient and starch agar plates. All three substrates i.e. potato, cassava and rice, showed the highest mean enzyme activity at 48 hours after incubation, followed by a gradual decline in activity over time. Potato supported the highest glucose production during the first 48 hours, indicating rapid enzymatic breakdown. Both Potato and Cassava maintained positive enzyme activity up to 72 h. Rice produced the lowest glucose levels throughout, implying limited enzymatic accessibility under the conditions tested. These results highlight the importance of the choice of starch substrate and the timing of enzymatic conversion for desired outputs to scale up microbial enzyme production.

Keywords: *Alpha Amylase, Starch-degrading enzymes, Starch substrates, Soil bacteria*